

Ritualized Expressions in Spanish as a Foreign Language Textbooks: Multimodal Pragmatic Annotation and Reliability of Large Language Models

Basilio Andrés Salas González

a74441@ualg.pt

Universidade do Algarve

Ritualized expressions constitute a fundamental, yet insufficiently theorized, component of communicative competence in Spanish as a foreign language (ELE). Despite their high frequency in everyday interaction and their relevance to the management of interpersonal relationships, current pedagogical materials often provide a limited grammatical and pragmatic representation of these expressions or present them without a coherent situational framework that would help learners understand the appropriate conditions for their use. This paper analyzes the pragmatic representation of ritualized expressions in a multimodal corpus of ELE textbooks aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), to identify prototypical contextual parameters that can contribute to both linguistic theory and instructional design.

The study sits at the intersection of phraseological theory, sociopragmatics, discourse analysis, and computational linguistics. A theoretical perspective inspired by the Meaning–Text tradition and subsequent developments in pragmatic phraseology is adopted, with particular emphasis on the notion of the *pragmateme*. Although terminological variation exists in the literature, where terms such as *phraseme*, *ritualized expression*, or *conversational routine* are used, these units share the property of being indexically anchored to recurrent social interactions. Analyzing their representation in teaching materials provides empirical evidence for debates about the relationship between linguistic conventionality, context-dependent meaning, and language acquisition.

The objects of study comprise five major classes of ritualized expressions: greetings and farewells, interjectional expressions, vocatives, politeness formulae, and profanities. These units are examined not merely as isolated lexical items, but as multimodal discursive resources whose interpretation depends on multiple situational cues. This encompasses the notion of the *Utterance Situation (SIT)*, operationalized through a set of pragmatic traits: (i) number of participants and participation structure; (ii) social and hierarchical relationships between interlocutors; (iii) spatial and temporal parameters of the interaction; (iv) type of communicative activity (institutional or informal; public or private); (v) dialogue tone; (vi) propositional content of the message; (vii) and expected response to the ritualized expression; Additionally, (viii) a possible translational equivalence in English; and where visual information permits, (ix) cues relating to implicit prosody, gestures, and inferred illocutionary force are considered.

From an epistemological and pedagogical standpoint, the analysis of these expressions is essential for understanding the development of pragmatic competence in ELE learners. Learning based on decontextualized lists of linguistic forms is insufficient for effective communication; contextualized exposure, by contrast, enables learners to form associations between expressions and concrete social situations, facilitating memory retention, transfer, and pragmatic appropriateness in real interactions.

The study draws on a multimodal corpus composed of various textbooks and lexicographic resources used across diverse educational contexts, including university programs, language schools, and adult education centers in Europe and the Americas. The materials span proficiency levels from A1 to B2 and include both international ELE textbook series and supplementary resources containing visual representations.

To facilitate large-scale annotation of multimodal data, the study incorporates the use of various large language models (LLMs). These systems are adapted through instruction-engineering techniques grounded in the adopted theoretical framework and are employed to generate structured descriptions of the contextual parameters represented in textbook images. The results are compiled in tabulated databases and subsequently reviewed by expert annotators. Particular attention is paid to identifying hallucinations, interpretive inconsistencies, and instances of pragmatic overgeneralization.

A central component of the work consists of evaluating inter-annotator reliability across different models and comparing automatic annotation with human annotation. The analysis combines quantitative measures of agreement with a qualitative examination of errors to determine both the current potential and the limitations of multimodal models in pragmatic interpretation. Preliminary results show varying levels of convergence across systems, as well as recurring difficulties in identifying implicit social hierarchies, nuances of interactional tone, and culturally specific routines. These findings underscore the need to develop theoretically grounded annotation guidelines and highlight the importance of critically evaluating computational tools in linguistic research.

The work makes contributions across several fields. It is the contextual construction of meaning in conventionalized utterances that provides empirical evidence for the philosophy of language and accounts for the function of ritualized acts as social signals. In computational linguistics, it proposes a methodology for integrating LLM-assisted annotation into multimodal corpus studies, while raising epistemological questions about the automatic interpretation of pragmatic meaning. Finally, in the field of language teaching, it formulates recommendations for the design of ELE materials that may allow for a richer and more contextualized representation of ritualized expressions.

Keywords: *Ritualized expressions; ELE; Multimodal discourse; Corpus annotation; Large language models*

References

- Blanco Escoda, X., & Mejri, S. (2018). *Les pragmatèmes*. Classiques Garnier.
- Blanco Escoda, X., & Sfar, I. (2018). *Lexicologie(s): Approches croisées en sémantique lexicale* (Vol. 242). Peter Lang.
- Bravo, D., Flores, N. H., & Cordisco, A. (2009). *Aportes pragmáticos, sociopragmáticos y socioculturales a los estudios de la cortesía en español*. EDICE.
- Brodersen, L. (2019). El acto de habla “saludar” en los manuales de ELE del español de la Argentina. *Quintú Quimün: Revista de Lingüística*, (3). <https://revele.uncoma.edu.ar/index.php/lingustica/article/view/2459>
- Cepeda Ruiz, C. Y. (2022). [Review of the book *Las fórmulas de saludo y de despedida en las lenguas románicas: Sincronía, diacronía y aplicación a la enseñanza*, by A. Zieliński, Ed.]. *Anuario de Letras. Lingüística y Filología*, 10(2), 245–250. <https://doi.org/10.19130/iifl.adel.2022.10.2.x00s25882>
- Félix-Brasdefer, J. C., & Placencia, M. E. (Eds.). (2019). *Pragmatic variation in service encounter interactions across the Spanish-speaking world*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351065382>
- Galloso Camacho, M. V., & Martín Márquez, E. (2023). Fraseología y discurso oral en la serie *La que se avecina*. *Doxa Comunicación: Revista Interdisciplinar de Estudios de Comunicación y Ciencias Sociales*, 36, 145–162. <https://doi.org/10.31921/doxacom.n36a1717>
- Galloso Camacho, M. V., & Tinoco Pérez, J. A. (2020). El uso de pragmatemas: La guerra de las galaxias y la saga de Harry Potter. *Cuadernos de Literatura*, 15, 32. <https://doi.org/10.30972/clt.0154681>
- Gharbi, N. (2018). Les pragmatèmes d’affect: Délimitation définitoire et propriétés sémantico-pragmatiques. *Lublin Studies in Modern Languages and Literature*, 42(4), 150–167.
- Instituto Cervantes. (2022). *Marco común europeo de referencia para las lenguas: Aprendizaje, enseñanza, evaluación*. https://cvc.cervantes.es/ensenanza/biblioteca_ele/marco/presentacion.htm
- Jirado Ayola, A. C., & Julio Correa, A. D. (2017). *Expresiones de cortesía en la interacción locutor oyente del programa Marcando a Tiempo, de Radio Tiempo Cartagena* [Trabajo de grado, Universidad de Cartagena]. Repositorio Universidad de Cartagena. <https://hdl.handle.net/11227/5583>
- Leontaridi, E., Soler, N., & Gómez Laguna, I. (2023). La expresión de la probabilidad mediante futuros y condicionales en manuales de ELE. *Ogigia*, 34, 99–132. <https://doi.org/10.24197/ogigia.34.2023.99-132>

Macías Chacón, M. del M. (2025). Étude préliminaire des marqueurs conversationnels chez les francophones et dans les manuels de FLE de niveau B2. *Langues & Parole*, 10, 165–178. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/languesparole.149>

Mel'čuk, I. (2020). Clichés and pragmatemes. *Neophilologica*, 32, 9–20. <https://doi.org/10.31261/NEO.2020.32.01>

Real Academia Española. (n.d.). Vocativo, vocativa. In *Diccionario de la lengua española* (electronic version). Retrieved January 21, 2025, from <https://dle.rae.es/vocativo>

Salas González, B. A. (2024). *Greetings and farewells: Pragmatic description for Spanish as a foreign language* [Preprint]. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381552562_Greetings_and_farewells_Pragmatic_description_for_Spanish_as_a_Foreign_Language

Stenström, A.-B. (2019). Los vocativos. In M. E. Placencia & X. A. Padilla (Eds.), *Guía práctica de pragmática del español*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351109239-8>

Stubbs, J., & Pustejovsky, J. (2012). *Natural language annotation for machine learning*. O'Reilly.

Webson, A., & Pavlick, E. (2022). Do prompt-based models really understand the meaning of their prompts? In M. Carpuat, M.-C. de Marneffe, & I. V. Meza Ruiz (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies* (pp. 2300–2344). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.167>

Zhao, T. Z., Wallace, E., Feng, S., Klein, D., & Singh, S. (2021). *Calibrate before use: Improving few-shot performance of language models* (arXiv:2102.09690). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2102.09690>